

PLANT SYMBOLISM IN THE VICTORIAN AGE OF ENGLISH
LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This thesis details the symbols of Victorian plants of English literature. In English literature, flowers are illuminated as a symbol of the inner experiences of people, their relationship.

Key words: symbol, friendship, emotion, Victorian era, traditions, time, culture.

Flowers have held significant meanings and conveyed coded messages for centuries, but the Victorian era provided particular opportunities for floral communication. Social convention imposed severe restrictions on what could be expressed directly, so people used flowers to flirt and send secret messages. ‘Le Langage des Fleurs’, the first dictionary to explain the meanings behind various flowers, was published in 1819 in Paris, and introduced a code which became extremely popular with the middle and upper classes of Victorian society, who were bound by strict etiquette. The symbolic meaning of each flower was often provided by its nature. For example, the mimosa symbolised chastity because its leaves close up at night or when touched, matching the behaviour of a chaste person. Popular floral meanings in the Victorian era included honeysuckle for the sweetness and bonds of love, and roses representing love – a symbol still understood today. Messages were traditionally conveyed via bouquets of herbs and flowers called ‘tussie-mussies’; the receiver would respond by holding the bouquet in a certain way to display acceptance, acknowledgement and approval.

The language of flowers, also known as floriography, has impacted the arts since the Victorian era. For instance, John Steinbeck centred his short story 'The Chrysanthemums' around the symbolism of these flowers, which are often seen to represent optimism and lost love. Floriography has also played its part on occasions such as the royal wedding between Kate Middleton and Prince William, when the bride's bouquet held very special and important meanings: lily of the valley to symbolise trustworthiness and the return of happiness; sweet William to represent gallantry (as well as sharing the name of her husband-to-be); hyacinth to show the constancy of love; and finally myrtle, representing love and marriage, which has been part of royal wedding tradition since Queen Victoria's reign, with sprigs of myrtle grown in the garden at Osborne, the former royal residence on the Isle of Wight, included in the bridal bouquet.

Aloe meant “bitterness,” pomegranate, “conceit,” and rhododendrons meant “danger.”

In most Ancient cultures, Aloe was a potent symbol of spiritual well-being and grace. It was such a holy symbol to the Mahometans of Egypt that they would hang the plant near the door of their home to signify their devotion to their gods. In later Roman culture, the plant’s sap was dried out and offered to the gods on burning coals as a form of incense. Aloe symbolizes good fortune, health, and beauty in many ancient cultures. However, in Victorian times, it was a symbol of superstition or grief instead.

Symbol of death and fertility

In Greek mythology, the pomegranate was known as the ‘fruit of the dead’ as it was said to have arisen from the blood of Adonis. It also prominently featured in the myth of Hades and Persephone. Hades, God of the underworld, used pomegranate seeds to trick Persephone into returning to the underworld for a few months of every year. Alongside death, the pomegranate symbolised fertility in Ancient Greece and Rome. It had a strong association to Aphrodite, the Greek goddess of love, as well as Hera, the Greek goddess of marriage and childbirth. In Ancient Rome, newlywed women wore crowns woven from pomegranate leaves, and the juice of pomegranates was used to cure infertility.

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